

RP-HPLC method development and validation for the estimation of furazolidone in bulk and pharmaceutical dosage form

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Abstract:

A reversed-phase high-performance liquid chromatography (RP-HPLC) method was developed and validated for the estimation of Furazolidone in bulk and tablet dosage forms. The separation was achieved on a Princeton C₁₈ analytical column (150 mm × 4.6 mm i.d., 5.0 μm) acetonitrile: [trimethylamine (0.02% in water)] (65:35), as mobile phase, and at a flow rate of 1.0 ml/min. The detection was carried out using a PDA detector at 366 nm. The total chromatographic analysis time per sample was about 6.0 min, with FUR eluting at a retention time of about 1.76±0.3 min. The method was validated for accuracy, precision, specificity, linearity, and sensitivity as per ICH guidelines. The standard curve was linear over the concentration range of 5-25 μg/ml with R² value 0.9991. The limit of detection (LOD) and limit of quantitation (LOQ) obtained for FUR were 0.39 μg/ml and 1.32 μg/ml respectively. The developed and validated method was successfully applied for the quantitative analysis of FUR in a 100 mg Tablet. The high recovery and low retention time confirm the suitability of the proposed method for the determination of FUR in regular assay and quality control analysis.

Keywords: Furazolidone, RP-HPLC, Tablets, Validation, and ICH.

I. Introduction:

Furazolidone (FUR) chemically called 3-[(E)-(5-nitrofuran-2-yl) methylideneamino]-1, 3-oxazolidin-2-one⁽¹⁾ (Fig.1) with molecular weight 225.16 and molecular formula is C₈H₇N₃O₅. FUR is a derivative of nitrofuran with antibacterial and antiprotozoal activities. FUR binds bacterial DNA which leads to the gradual inhibition of monoamine oxidase. FUR is used in the treatment of diarrhoea caused by giardia infection⁽²⁾⁽³⁾. FUR is active against the protozoan Giardia lamblia (Giardia intestinalis) and against a range of bacteria in vitro including staphylococci, enterococci, Escherichia coli, Salmonella spp., Shigella spp., and Vibrio cholera. FUR is bactericidal and appears to act by interfering with bacterial enzyme systems⁽¹⁾. FUR and its related free radical products are believed to bind DNA and induce cross-links. Bacterial DNA is particularly susceptible to this drug, leading to high levels of mutations (transitions and transversions) in the bacterial chromosome⁽²⁾. It is yellow or yellow with a greenish tint, odourless, fine crystalline powder. It is not hygroscopic, slightly soluble in dimethylformamide, very slightly soluble in acetone, practically insoluble in water, and 96% alcohol and it is soluble in acetonitrile and dimethyl sulfoxide. FUR melting point is 280°C⁽⁴⁾. It is commercially available as tablets (100 mg) and suspension (25mg) and is prescribed four times daily for seven to ten days with a half-life of 10 minutes⁽²⁾.

Several methods have been employed for the estimation of FUR alone and in combination using different analytical techniques such as HPLC ⁽³⁾⁽⁶⁾⁽⁷⁾⁽⁸⁾, HPTLC ⁽⁹⁾, UV-Visible Spectrophotometry ⁽⁵⁾⁽¹⁰⁾. However, these methods were limited to high retention times and usage of complex buffers making these methods less reliable. Hence, the current study aimed to develop a simple, cost-effective, and accurate RP-HPLC method using PDA detection for determination of FUR in its API and dosage form and validated as per ICH guidelines. ⁽¹¹⁾

Fig 1: Structure of Furazolidone

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

Acetonitrile (ACN) of HPLC grade by Sigma Aldrich, Triethylamine (TEA) of AR grade by SD Fine Chem Limited, and water from the Milli-Q RO framework (Millipore, Bedford, USA) were used. The working standard of FUR was obtained as a gift sample from the Indian Pharmacopoeia Commission (IPC), New Delhi, India.

2.2. Instrumentation

Shimadzu UV-Visible spectrophotometer UV-1700 (190-1100nm), Ultrasonicator (LABMAN), Waters Alliance HPLC system configured as follows: 2545 Quaternary Gradient module pump, 2998 photodiode array with semi-prep flow cell detector, manual prep injector configured with a 10 ml loop, and Waters fraction collector 3. Software used was ChromScope, Analytical column used was Princeton C₁₈ column (150 mmx4.6 mm i.d, 5micron particle size).

2.3. Preparation of Standard Solutions

FUR solution was prepared by dissolving accurately about 10 mg of standard in acetonitrile and making up the volume and this solution was refrigerated at 2-8°C. From the standard solution working stock solution of 100 µg/mL, FUR was prepared. From the working stock solution, aliquots of 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, and 2.5 mL were transferred in a series of 10 mL volumetric flasks and diluted up to mark with mobile phase to get the concentration range of 5, 10, 15, 20 and 25 µg/mL of FUR.

2.4. Preparation of Sample Solution

Tablets FUR 100 mg, was obtained as a gift sample from Low Cost Standard Therapeutics (LOCOST). Ten tablets of the marketed formulation of Furazolidone (FUR 100mg) were weighed accurately, powdered, and the weight of the powder equivalent to 10 mg of FUR was transferred to 100 ml volumetric flask, dissolved the contents with acetonitrile and filtered to obtain a concentration of 100 µg/ml of Furazolidone. The above solution was further diluted with acetonitrile to achieve concentrations of 10 µg/ml.

2.5. Method Validation

Validation of the method for specificity, linearity, accuracy, precision, range, quantitation limit, detection limit, robustness, and system suitability as per the ICH guidelines ⁽¹¹⁾.

2.5.1. Accuracy

It is defined as the closeness of obtained value to that of the true value. Accuracy is calculated as percentage recovery for formulation.

2.5.2. Precision

Evaluation of precision was carried out by inter-day and intra-day comparison study samples consisting of the concentration (six replicates) of 10 $\mu\text{g/mL}$.

2.5.3. Specificity

Specificity is demonstrated as the analyte response measurement in the presence of excipients.

2.5.4. Limit of Detection (LOD) and Limit of Quantification (LOQ)

The determination of LOD and LOQ was assessed by the signal-to-noise ratio. The LOD ratio was 3:1 whereas the LOQ of the drug could be quantified with a minimum peak area in the ratio of 10:1.

2.5.5. Linearity

The average of six determinations at five concentration levels covering the range of 5-25 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ for, FUR the evaluation of linearity was performed.

2.5.6. Ruggedness and Robustness

The alteration in the condition of the experiment like operators, the source of reagents, similar type columns, and optimized conditions like wavelength, mobile phase ratio, and flow rate were used as an assessment tool for the ruggedness and robustness monitoring.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Specificity

No peaks were eluted along with the retention time of FUR hence, the developed method was specific for the determination of FUR in the formulation (Fig.4).

Fig 2: HPLC chromatogram of Blank

Fig 3: HPLC chromatogram of FUR Standard

Fig 4: HPLC chromatogram of FUR Sample

3.2. Linearity

The evaluation of the method to be linear was by six determinations at five concentration levels with a range of 5-25 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ for FUR (Fig.5).

Fig 5: Calibration curve of FUR

3.3. Accuracy

The accuracy of the method was carried out for the quality control samples by recovery method and the accuracy was found to be 98.7 % - 99.05% (Table 1).

3.4. Precision

Calculation of the precision method was carried out by the intra-day and inter-day precision studies at the concentration of 5, 15, and 25 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ and they were found to be within the limits (Table 1).

Table 1. Accuracy and Precision studies of

Sample ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Amount found ($\mu\text{g/ml}$) Mean \pm SD*	Accuracy (% Recovery)	Precision (% RSD) **	
			Inter day	Intra day
5	4.45 \pm 0.34	98.7	1.7	1.2
15	14.5 \pm 0.27	99.0 5	1.08	1.2
25	24.7 \pm 0.04	98.9 6	1.3	1.6

Furazolidone

*SD: Standard Deviation

**RSD: Relative Standard Deviation

3.5. Limit of Detection and Limit of Quantification

The lowest limit detected for the method for FUR was at 0.39 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ based on the signal-to-noise ratio 3:1. Due to the increase in the sensitivity of the method, quantification was done at 1.32 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ for FUR (Table 2).

Table 2: LOD and LOQ

Sample	LOD ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	LOQ ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)
FUR	0.39	1.32

3.6. Ruggedness and Robustness

When alteration in the condition of the experiment was done and change of instruments, no notable changes in the parameters of the chromatogram were observed, proving that the developed method was found to be highly rugged and robust.

3.7. Assay

Estimation of FUR in dosage forms by the HPLC method was carried out using the optimized chromatographic conditions. The sample solution was prepared and the chromatogram was recorded. The percentage of the drug found in the formulation and standard deviation were calculated and presented in Table 3. The result of the analysis shows that the amount of drug was in good agreement with the label claim of the formulation.

Table 3. Assay and recovery studies for FUR formulation

Formulation*	Label claim (mg)	Estimated amount (mg) Mean \pm SD (n = 6)
T1	100	98.4 \pm 0.26

* Marketed formulation

3.9. System suitability

System suitability parameters such as number of theoretical plates, HETP and peak tailing are determined. The results obtained are shown in Table 5. The number of theoretical plates for FUR was 71212.6799.

Table 5: Results of system suitability parameters

Parameters	FUR
Area	71212.67
No of Theoretical Plates	5547.57
Tailing Factor	1.1
Asymmetry Factor	0.9

IV. CONCLUSION:

In the present study, the developed method includes a simple, rapid, cost effective HPLC-PDA method using a simple mobile phase system [ACN: TEA (0.02% in water)], low retention time and furtherly, the optimized method was validated as per the International Conference on Harmonisation (ICH) Q2B Guidelines. The standard curve was linear over the concentration range of 5-25 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ with R^2 value 0.9991. The limit of detection (LOD) and limit of quantitation (LOQ) were 0.39 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and 1.32 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ respectively. The selective quantification of FUR with no

interference from formulation excipients, high percentage recovery and low retention times made this method applicable for routine quantitative analysis of FUR in bulk and pharmaceutical dosage forms. This method can be further incorporated with kinetic degradation studies and also be used for estimation in different biological fluids.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest

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References:

1. Mittan DS, Kumar P, Prasad SV. Development and validation of new RP-HPLC method for the estimation of furazolidone in bulk and solid dosage form. *Analytical Chemistry An Indian Journal*, 2008; 7(11): 817-9.
2. <https://go.drugbank.com/drugs/DB006>
3. Prasad CV, Sripriya V, Saha RN, Parimoo P. Simultaneous determination of tinidazole, furazolidone and diloxanide furoate in a combined tablet preparation by second- derivative spectrophotometry. *Journal of pharmaceutical and biomedical analysis*. 1999Dec 1; 21(5):961-8.
4. Beliatskaya AV, Krasnyuk II, Elagina AO, Krasnyuk II, Kashlikova IM, Stepanova OI, Vorob'yov AN, Kuzmenko AN, Iskenderova SG, Kannieva DR. Study of the solubility of furazolidone from solid dispersions with polyvinylpyrrolidone. *Moscow University Chemistry Bulletin*. 2020 Jan;75:43-6.
5. Mittan DS, Kumar P, Prasad SV, Kumar L, Kumar S. Development and validation of new spectroscopic method for the estimation of furazolidone in bulk and solid dosage form. *Oriental Journal of Chemistry*. 2008; 24(3):1009-12.
6. Pietruszka KA, Olejinik M, Sell B. Development and validation of a liquid chromatography method for the determination of nitrofurans in water. *Bulletin-veterinary institute in pulawy*. 2007 Jan 1; 51(2):267-70.
7. Sivaperuman A, Nagarajan NC, Jayapaul U. Simultaneous RP-HPLC estimation and validation of metronidazole, furazolidone, and dicyclomine in capsule. *Journal of Reports in Pharmaceutical Sciences*. 2021 Jan 1; 10(1):15-21.
8. Murali D, Rambabu C. Simultaneous determination of metronidazole and furazolidone in combined tablet dosage form: Development and validation of a stability indicating HPLC method. *Analytical Chemistry An Indian Journal*. 2016; 16:1-2.
9. Kavitha J, Krishna KC, Iakshmi K. Simultaneous estimation of metronidazole, furazolidone and loperamide by HPTLC in veterinary formulation. *J Pharm Sci*. 2013;5: 620-5.
10. Jain R, Jain N, Jain DK, Patel VK, Rajak H, Jain SK. Novel UV spectrophotometer methods for quantitative estimation of metronidazole and furazolidone using mixed hydrotrophy solubilization. *Arabian Journal of Chemistry*. 2017 Feb 1; 10(2):151-6.
11. International conference on harmonisation of technical requirements for registration of pharmaceuticals for human use ICH harmonised tripartite guideline validation of analytical procedures: text and methodology Q2(R1).